

Recent Spin Results at PHENIX

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The logo for the PHENIX experiment. It features the word "PHENIX" in a bold, black, sans-serif font. The letter "E" is replaced by a stylized sunburst or starburst symbol. Above the "E" is a red, curved line that resembles a bird in flight or a wing.

PHENIX Experiment

- Central Arms ($|\eta| < 0.35$)
 - Tracking: DC and PC
 - EM Calorimeter
- Forward Arms
 - Muon arms ($1.2 < |\eta| < 2.4$)
 - Zero Degree Calorimeter (ZDC)
- Completed data collection in 2016

Gluon Spin

- ▶ Gluon helicity distribution function $\Delta g(x)$ is measured to find ΔG , the gluon spin contribution.

$$\Delta G \equiv \int_0^1 \Delta g(x) dx$$

- ▶ The $\Delta g(x)$ is found via the longitudinal double spin asymmetry, A_{LL}

Polarized PDFs

Parton-level hard scattering cross section calculable in pQCD

$$A_{LL} \equiv \frac{\sigma_{++} - \sigma_{+-}}{\sigma_{++} + \sigma_{+-}} \propto \frac{\sum_{a,b,c=q,\bar{q},g} \Delta f_a \otimes \Delta f_b \otimes d\hat{\sigma}^{f_a f_b \rightarrow f_c X} \otimes D_{f_c}^{\pi^0}}{\sum_{a,b,c=q,\bar{q},g} f_a \otimes f_b \otimes \hat{\sigma}^{f_a f_b \rightarrow f_c X} \otimes D_{f_c}^{\pi^0}}$$

Unpolarized PDFs

Fragmentation functions from e+e- scattering

Charged Pion A_{LL} at 510 GeV

- First PHENIX measurement at 510 GeV
- Consistent with DSSV global fits within statistical uncertainty

Phys. Rev. D 102, 032001 (2020)

- Charged pions potential indicator for sign of Δg via pion A_{LL} ordering

Direct Photon A_{LL} at 510 GeV

- First PHENIX direct photon cross section and A_{LL} at 510 GeV
- “Golden” channel to access gluon polarization since hard interaction is mostly q-g
 - No color interactions by photon

Jet A_{LL} at 510 GeV

- First jet A_{LL} at PHENIX
 - Unfolded to correct for underlying event and detector effects
- Cross section below NLO prediction
 - Similar to LHC finding for small R

Origin of TSSAs

- Transverse momentum dependent (TMD) distributions and fragmentations
 - Siverson effect (initial state): correlation between nucleon spin and parton momentum
 - Collins effect (final state): correlation between fragmenting parton and hadron transverse momentum
- Multi-parton correlation in collinear framework
 - Initial state or in fragmentation process
 - SSA appears as twist-3 observable

$$A_N = \frac{\sigma^\uparrow - \sigma^\downarrow}{\sigma^\uparrow + \sigma^\downarrow}$$

η and π^0 A_N at 200 GeV

- Sensitive to both initial and final state effects
- Mid-rapidity sensitive to gluon spin-momentum correlations
- New data significantly improves precision
- Asymmetries consistent with zero

Direct Photon A_N at 200 GeV

- Sensitive to initial state effects
 - Production dominated by $q+g \rightarrow q+\gamma$
- First measurement at PHENIX
 - Accepted by PRL (arXiv:2102.13585[hep-ex])
 - Help constrain trigluon correlation function

Open Heavy Flavor Electron A_N at 200 GeV

- Mostly produced by gg at RHIC energies
- Sensitive to trigluon correlations in collinear framework
- Dominant contribution from open Charm production
- Asymmetry consistent with zero within uncertainty

Neutron A_N at 200 GeV

- Forward measurement ($\eta > 6.8$)
- Nuclear dependent neutron A_N
(PRL 120, 022001 (2018))
- P_T dependence of A_N in p+p (PRD 103, 032007 (2021))
- Asymmetry show p_T dependence and broken down in X_F and detector activity
 - Enhance/suppress UPC contribution

Summary

- PHENIX spin program continues to elucidate our understanding of QCD
- Results:
 - Longitudinal spin analyses:
 - Jet, direct photon, charged pion A_{LL}
 - Transverse spin analyses:
 - Direct photon, π^0 and η , heavy flavor electron, and neutron A_N
- Still more to come in the future!